

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of pyruvic acid by peroxomonophosphate in acid perchlorate medium

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Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of pyruvic acid by peroxomonophosphate (PMP) has been studied in a wider pH range. The stoichiometry corresponds to the reaction as represented by the eq. (1)

The pattern of reactivity of peroxomonophosphate species has been delineated. A plausible reaction mechanism is suggested. The energy and entropy of activation were calculated to be (72 ± 7) kJ mol⁻¹ and (-40 ± 4) JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

Keywords : Peroxomonophosphate, kinetics, pyruvic acid, oxidation.

Introduction

The kinetic studies reported¹⁻⁵ for the oxidation of various substrates by peroxodiphosphate in acid medium are more or less substantiated through the hydrolytic product of the per acid. Peroxodiphosphate in aqueous acid medium involves hydrolysis as the rate controlling step which is followed by faster reactions with peroxomonophosphate. However, oxidation⁶ of hypohosphorous acid by peroxodiphosphate is one such reaction where hydrolysis and oxidation steps are of comparable rates. The oxidation of nitrite⁷, hydroxylamine⁸, bromide⁹, EDTA¹⁰ and a few organic compounds¹¹⁻¹³ by peroxomonophosphate are also reported in both acid and alkaline media. However, further studies are required to understand the chemistry of this per-acid so that a general pattern of reactivity can be ascertained. The title study was therefore, undertaken to understand more chemistry of peroxomonophosphate as an oxidant with additional enquiries such as :

(i) The trace metal ion catalysis by metal ions such as Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} has earlier been reported^{14,15} in oxidation of certain organic compounds by peroxodiphosphate.

(ii) The reduction product of peroxomonophosphate is phosphate, such a product has any role to play in delineating the reaction events in the mechanism is an important question to probe further.

(iii) The hydrolysis of the per-acid to H₂O₂ is an impor-

tant aspect. It is important to probe further whether or not H₂O₂ is formed in hydrolysis of peroxodiphosphate under experimental conditions.

Experimental

The solutions of peroxomonophosphoric acid (heretofore written as PMP) were prepared¹⁶ by hydrolysing peroxodiphosphate in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ at 45 °C for 1.5 h as and when required. Furthermore, the tests of H₂O₂ as a hydrolysing product were negative even for the time of storing PMP solution at refrigerated temperature (~ 5 °C). All other chemicals were either of B.D.H. AnalaR or E. Merck G.R. quality and were used as supplied. Doubly distilled water was employed. However, in a few cases doubly distilled water was further re-distilled in the presence of EDTA to remove trace metal ions to eliminate the effect of these ions, if any, on the rate of the reaction.

Kinetic procedure :

The reaction mixtures containing pyruvic acid, HClO₄ and other required chemicals were taken in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks which were suspended in a thermostated water-bath at ± 0.1 °C unless stated otherwise. The reaction was initiated by adding the requisite volume of desired concentration of temperature per-equilibrated PMP into the reaction mixture. The progress of the reaction was monitored by estimating PMP iodometrically. An aliquot (5 or 10 cm³) of the reaction

mixture was withdrawn at different intervals of time and then released into an ice-cold ~10% solution of potassium iodide.

It was also observed that different samples of peroxodiphosphate gave varying results, therefore, the same batch of sample of peroxodiphosphate was employed throughout the study for the preparation of peroxomonophosphate.

Initial rates were computed¹⁷ employing plane mirror method. Pseudo-first order plots were made wherever reaction conditions permitted. Second order plots were also made for comparable concentrations of the reactants to evaluate second order rate constants. Triplicate rate measurements were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$.

The stoichiometric reactions were carried out in thermostated water bath maintained at 45 ± 0.1 °C under the conditions of $[\text{PMP}] > [\text{Pyr}]$ in $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ for ca. 2 h ('Pyr' is heretofore written for pyruvic acid). The excess peroxomonophosphoric acid was measured iodometrically and the results corresponded to the reaction as represented by the eq. (1)

where $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3-$

The presence CO_2 was tested by lime water and that of acetate ions by neutral ferric chloride solution qualitatively.

Results and discussion

The concentration of PMP was varied in the range $(1.0-10.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients at pH 4.04 and 45 °C. Initial rates (k_i , $\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) were computed and a plot of initial rate (k_i) versus $[\text{PMP}]$ yielded a straight line passing through the origin indicating first order dependence with respect peroxomonophosphate.

The concentration of pyruvic acid was varied in the range $(1.0-5.0) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients at pH 4.04 and 45 °C. Pseudo-first order plots were made and the pseudo-first order rate constants (k' , s^{-1}) were plotted against the concentration of pyruvic acid that yielded a straight line passing through the origin confirming first order with respect to pyruvic acid. However second order was further confirmed by second order plots. The second order rate constants (k , $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) calculated from these plots agreed with those obtained from initial rates and pseudo-first order rate constants respectively (Table 1).

The rate dependence is complex if one takes into account the plot of rate constant (k , $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) versus pH. The effect of ionic strength was studied by employing lithium perchlorate. The rate remains unchanged on variation of lithium perchlorate. The energy and entropy of activation were calculated to be $(72 \pm 7) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $(-40 \pm 4) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

Table 1. Initial rates (k_i), pseudo-first order rate constants (k') and second order rate constants (k) in the reaction of peroxomonophosphoric acid and pyruvic acid

pH = 4.04, temp. 45 °C				
$10^3 [\text{PMP}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^2 [\text{Pyr}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^6 (k_i)$ ($\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$10^4 (k')$ (s^{-1})	$10^2 k$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
1.0	1.0	-	4.22	4.7 - 4.2
2.0	1.0	0.87	-	4.4 4.3 -
3.0	1.0	1.33	-	4.8 4.4 -
4.0	1.0	1.83	-	4.7 4.5 -
5.0	1.0	2.33	-	4.5 4.6 -
6.0	1.0	2.66	-	4.7 4.4 -
8.0	1.0	3.66	-	4.9 4.6 -
10.0	1.0	4.66	-	- 4.6 -
1.0	2.0	-	8.82	- - 4.3
2.0	2.0	-	8.70	- - 4.3
3.0	2.0	2.83	-	- - -
4.0	2.0	3.66	-	4.5 - -
5.0	2.0	4.33	-	4.8 - -
6.0	2.0	5.3	-	4.4 - -
8.0	2.0	7.33	-	4.6 - -

Table-1 (contd.)

10.0	2.0	9.33	4.6	-	-	-
1.0	1.0	-	4.22	4.7	-	4.2
1.0	1.5	-	6.52	4.4	-	4.3
1.0	2.0	-	8.44	-	-	4.2
1.0	2.5	-	10.2	-	-	4.1
1.0	3.0	-	12.4	-	-	4.1
1.0	3.5	-	14.3	-	-	4.1
1.0	4.0	-	16.3	-	-	4.1
1.0	4.5	-	18.2	-	-	4.1
1.0	5.0	-	20.2	-	-	4.1
2.0	1.0	8.86	-	4.8	4.5	4.3
2.0	1.5	-	-	4.8	-	4.2
2.0	2.0	-	8.44	-	-	4.1
2.0	2.5	-	10.2	-	-	4.1
2.0	3.0	-	12.1	-	-	4.1
2.0	3.5	-	14.3	-	-	4.1
2.0	4.0	-	16.3	-	-	4.1
2.0	4.5	-	18.2	-	-	4.1
2.0	5.0	-	20.2	-	-	4.1

The values in parenthesis were obtained from initial rates.

Values in the third column were obtained from pseudo-first order rate constants.

Values in first column were obtained from second order plots.

Kinetics were unaffected by phosphate ions, ascribing to the fact that there is no equilibrium involving phosphate and preceded by the rate determining step in the reaction mechanism. The trace amounts of Cu^{II}, Fe^{II} and H₂O₂ respectively also did not affect the rate of the reaction.

If the kinetic orders with respect to PMP and pyruvic acid are taken into account, there is no kinetic evidence for the formation of an intermediate complex. Various equilibria (2) to (4) involving PMP in aqueous solution are reported¹⁶ to account for the rate dependence on pH.

where K_1 , K_2 and K_3 are reported¹⁶ to be 8.0×10^{-2} , 4.2×10^{-6} and 1.6×10^{-13} mol dm⁻³ at 298 K and $I = 0.2$ mol dm⁻³. The pyruvic acid also undergoes dissociation

in aqueous solution as in eq. (5) and the dissociation constant (K_d) has been reported to be $\sim 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm³.

The pyruvic acid predominantly exists as a molecular species (Pyr) at pH < 1. The ratio of dissociated (Pyr⁻) and undissociated (Pyr) forms increases with increasing pH and practically all of pyruvic acid is converted to an anionic form at pH > 6.

Similarly per-acid at pH < 1, exists as H₃PO₅ and the ratio of dissociated and undissociated forms (H₂PO₅⁻/H₃PO₅) increases with increasing pH and virtually all of the per-acid exists as H₂PO₅⁻ at pH 3–7. On further increase in pH > 8, the second dissociation becomes appreciable. However, if one considers per-acid as a cationoid reagent (-P-O^{δ+}-H), the order of reactivity of the per-acid is as follows :

The species [PO₅³⁻] in the pH region 1–7 is negligible and [H₃PO₅] ≈ [H₂PO₅⁻] exists in the pH region 3–7. Since

the pH dependence is complex, this has been taken into account to understand the pattern of reactivity of each peroxomonopohate species and to delineate the pathways in a proper manner. Below pH ~3, from eqs. (2), (5) and following one

The rate law for the reaction is obtained as :

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMP}]}{dt} = \left\{ \frac{k_1 K_d}{K_1 + [\text{H}^+]} \right\} \left\{ \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_5][\text{Pyr}][\text{H}^+]}{([\text{H}^+] + K_d)} \right\} \quad (7)$$

$$k = \frac{k_1 K [\text{H}^+]}{K_1([\text{H}^+] + K_d)} \quad (8)$$

where 'k' is an observed second order rate constant.

The reciprocal of the eq. (8) on re-arrangement yields eq. (9)

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{K_1}{k_1 K_d} + \frac{K_1}{k_1 [\text{H}^+]} \quad (9)$$

A plot of $1/k$ versus $1/[\text{H}^+]$ yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 1). K_1/k_1 was calculated from the

slope to be 32.5, 22.5 and 10.5 s^{-1} and K_d from the intercept and gradient to be 5.9×10^{-4} , 6.3×10^{-4} and $9.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 35, 40 and 45 °C respectively. However, the value of ' K_d ' is slightly lower than the value reported earlier. If one takes into account the effect of ionic strength and also that of the temperature, such an agreement appears to be quite reasonable.

When $\text{pH} > 3$ and < 5 , the reactions (10) and (11) constitute the following mechanism.

Such a mechanism leads to the rate law (12) and (13)

$$\frac{d[\text{PMP}]}{dt} = \left(k'_2 + \frac{k'_2 K_d}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) [\text{PMP}][\text{Pyr}] \quad (12)$$

$$\text{and, } k' = k'_1 + \frac{k'_2 K_d}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

where k' is an observed second order rate constant.

If a plot between k' and $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ is made, this also yields a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 2). k'_1 ,

Fig. 1. Plot of $(k')^{-1}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ in the reaction of H_3PO_5 and pyruvic acid. $\text{pH} = 1.0-3.0$; $[\text{PMP}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{CH}_3\text{COCOONa}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (○) 35 °C; (▽) 40 °C and (□) 45 °C.

Fig. 2. Plot of (k') versus $[H^+]^{-1}$ in the reaction of H_3PO_5 and pyruvic acid. pH = 3.0-4.5; $[PMP] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[CH_3COCOONa] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (\odot) 35 °C; (∇) 40 °C and (\square) 45 °C.

calculated from the intercept was found to be 1.6×10^{-2} , 2.4×10^{-2} and $4.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k'_2 K_d$ from the slope to be 6.5×10^{-5} , 11.0×10^{-5} and $16.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35, 40 and 50 °C respectively. If K_d is taken into

account, most of the reaction events are governed by reaction step (10).

In the pH region > 5 but < 7 , the species HPO_5^- also becomes significant along with $H_2PO_5^-$ species, the fol-

Fig. 3. Plot of (k'') versus $[H^+]^{-1}$ in the reaction of H_3PO_5 and pyruvic acid. pH = 4.0-6.5; $[PMP] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[CH_3COCOONa] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (\odot) 35 °C; (∇) 40 °C and (\square) 45 °C.

lowing reaction mechanism is envisaged.

This leads to the rate law (16) and (17)

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMP}]}{dt} = \left(k_2'' + \frac{k_2'' K_2'}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) [\text{H}_2\text{PO}_5][\text{Pyr}] \quad (16)$$

$$\text{and } k'' = k_1'' + \frac{k_2'' K_2}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (17)$$

A plot of k'' versus $[\text{H}^+]$ from eq. (17) yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 3), k_1'' calculated from the gradient to be 6.0×10^{-2} , 11.0×10^{-2} and $17.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2'' K_2'$ from the gradient to be 4.78×10^{-8} , 6.25×10^{-8} and $6.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35, 40 and 45 °C respectively were obtained. These composite values of $k_2'' K_2'$ indicate that the reaction is still predominantly controlled by $\text{H}_2\text{PO}_5 + \text{Pyr}^-$ reaction.

A mechanism of nucleophilic attack on the peroxide oxygen in the oxidation by peroxides has been suggested by Edwards *et al.*⁷. The order of reactivity of PMP has been reported with bromide, nitrite, hydrazine and hydroxylamine in accord with the nucleophilic action of these reducing substances on the peroxide oxygen, the latter is known to exhibit dependence more on the polarizability and lesser on the basicity of nucleophiles. However, Gupta and coworkers agreeing to such an observation still suggest that such a mechanism should only be considered established when nucleophilic attack on oxygen is tenable in other redox systems involving peroxomonophosphoric acid. However, they disagree with the inclusion of hydrazine and hydroxylamine in above listed compounds on the premise that these are normally contaminated with trace metal ions as catalysts. Thus there is no direct attack of the nucleophile on the oxygen in catalyzed reactions.

If one pursues the rate constants with H_2PO_5 and H_2PO_5^- species, H_2PO_5 is a better oxidant than H_2PO_5^- due to the decrease of the positive charge on per-acid oxygen ($-\text{O}-\text{O}^{\delta+}-\text{H}$). Since hydrogen ion catalysis has been ob-

served in lower pH region ($\text{pH} < 3$), this can be accounted for in the reaction Scheme 1.

Such a Scheme 1 explains higher reactivity of H_3PO_5 as the elimination of phosphoric acid is facile from such an adduct in view of the fact that the P-O bond in phosphoric acid in the adduct has a high tendency for the formation of very stable P=O bond.

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